

DEVELOPMENT OF LINGUOCULTUROLOGY IN LINGUISTICS AND ITS THEORETICAL BASICS

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Abstract.

the article says about cognitive linguistics, its development, concept, which has been widely studied by world linguists as a cognitive, psycholinguistic, linguistic and cultural phenomenon, and it includes the subject areas of several scientific directions. The author makes scientific observations about the need for language not for the formation of concepts, but for concept exchange and discussion in the process of communication, concepts exist in the real mentality of people, therefore, it is necessary to express them verbally, that is, using language tools for communication.

Key words.

cognitive linguistics, linguoculturology, pragmatics, concept, conceptual analysis.

Modern linguistics, along with this, began to pay attention to cognitive science from the middle of the 20th century, and the first steps in this regard were taken by F. Boas, E. Sapir and B.L. American and Russian linguists like Whorf put it. Later, by the end of the 20th century, cognitive linguistics and scientific research in this regard were increasingly developing, and at the same time, many linguists were interested in linguistics. The interaction between humanity and language and its problems began to be widely analyzed. Gradually, as a linguistic-philosophical unit, the concept term appeared in the science of linguistics.

This term has entered the basis of linguistic culture, semantics and other fields of linguistics and is being analyzed in different ways. Although there is no clear definition of the term "concept" at the present time, many linguists have been theoretically studying and analyzing it in different ways. The definition of the term "concept" was first used in Aristotle's "Theory of Classical Concepts", and later this term was introduced by the philosopher Anselm (1033-1109). Also, the philosopher

and scientist Gottlob Frege defines the difference between concept and object in the philosophy of language in 1892. According to Frege, a sentence representing any unit consisting of a phrase denoting an object is called a concept³¹. This term is actively used in cognitive linguistics as a cognitive "communication" in a disappearing context, and when translated from Latin, it expresses various meanings: Conceptio- a) system, communication b) signing legal documents and giving various other meanings. Later, in Russian linguistics, this term began to be widely studied and analyzed, and the theoretical basis of the term "concept" was developed by several Russian scientists E.F. Karsky, A.A. Shakhmatov, A.A. Potebnja, A.N. Afanasiev, V.N. Telia, A.N. Sobolevsky, D.S. Likhachov, V.V. Vorobyev, V.A. Maslova, N.D. Arutyunova, E.S. Kubryakova, A.N. Morokovsky, N.K. Ryabtseva, V. Ayrapetyan, V.V. Kolesov, A.Ya. Organized by Gurevich, A. Wierzbicka, M. Minsky and others. Professor V.A. Maslova analyzed various definitions and gave his version: the term "concept" is a semantic unit that has linguistic and cultural characteristics and describes the speakers of any selected ethnoculture. The concept, reflecting the ethnic mindset, defines the image of the ethnic language world and serves as a brick for building "the house of our being".³²

Russian linguist V.Z. In his scientific work, Demyankov deeply analyzes the use of the term "concept" in different languages and gives conclusions on the meanings it is used in Russian, English, German, French, Italian, and Spanish languages. In particular, it acknowledges that in the Latin language "conceptus" means "primitive, initial state", and the words "konzept" and "concept" from the German language are used as "raw mold", that is, "Concept" in Russian. After deep analysis through his scientific works, V.Z. Demyankov interprets the meaning of the word "concept" based on the Latin meaning "initial meaning". Also V.Z. Analyzing the words "understanding" and "concept", Demyankov emphasizes that understanding is one of the logical forms of thinking, and that it serves to help people in the process of understanding reality.³³

Concept is a new and old term in linguistics. The word conceptus is derived from the medieval Latin word "concupere-consapere" which means "creating an idea, imagining". In classical Latin, the word conceptus also expressed meanings such as "pool", "inflammation", "microbe". Later, the word "concept" entered Roman and German languages with its derivatives (concept-concevoir in French, concetto-

³¹ Isomiddin Choliyev. "‘Concept’ in Modern Linguistics: The Component of the Concept ‘Good’ ." *Academia.edu*, www.academia.edu/21725734/_Concept_in_Modern_Linguistics_the_Component_of_the_Concept_Good_.

³² Maslova, V.A., (2004). *Cognitive linguistics*. Minsk: Tetra Systems, pp: 80

³³ Демьянков В.З. Понятие и концепт в художественной литературе и в научном языке. (2000).// Вопросы филологии. –Москва, 2001. № 1(7). –С.35-46

consepire in Italian, concepto-concebir in Spanish, conceito-conceber in Portuguese, concept-conceive in English).³⁴

As a central concept, the term concept has a special place in linguocultural and linguocognitology. However, in each field it expresses its own meaning and essence. This term was used for the first time by S. Askoldov in Russian linguistics in the first quarter of the 20th century, who defined the concept as a two-way communicative process, the main essence of which is considered important for the interaction of representatives of different nationalities.

Also, S.A. According to Askoldov, the cognitive concept is "the most complex flower bud of mental precision" and he emphasizes that the concept of knowledge is always related to some kind of objectivity-ideality or reality. Askoldov cites the word as an integral part of the concept.³⁵ In Russian linguistics, this term was used as a synonym for the term "concept" from the 1920s to the 1970s.

By the 80s of the 20th century, a greater need for this concept began to be felt. Concepts that arise in the human mind are based not only on the meaning of words taken from dictionaries, but on individual, national, cultural and historical experience, and the richer the experience, the wider the boundaries of understanding. The greater the possibility of the emergence of the emotional aura of the word, manifested in all aspects of the concept. The term "concept" has been used in the linguistic literature since the beginning of the 1990s by D.S. After the scientific works of Likhachev, S.A. Askoldov, it began to be widely used. D.S. Likhachev expresses a positive opinion about Askoldov's article, but he defines the essence of the concept and emphasizes that, unlike it, the concept is not for the word, but for the meaning of each word in the dictionary. In addition, he suggests to consider the concept as an algebraic expression used in our speech. S.A. Askoldov looks at the concept from the point of view of observation and evaluates it as a potential, dynamic structure. According to the scientist, the social situation and conditions, characteristics occupy a special place in order for a person to be able to fully express the meaning. A.S. Askoldov emphasizes the substitute function of the concept and states that it can replace some aspects of real objects or real reality.³⁶

³⁴ Isomiddin Choliyev. "‘Concept’ in Modern Linguistics: The Component of the Concept ‘Good’ ." Academia.edu, www.academia.edu/21725734/_Concept_in_Modern_Linguistics_the_Component_of_the_Concept_Good_.

³⁵ Аскольдов С. А. Концепт и слово // Русская словесность. От теории словесности к структуре текста. Антология / под общ. ред. В. П. Нерознака. М.: Academia, 1997. С. 267-269

³⁶ Аскольдов С. А. Концепт и слово // Русская словесность. От теории словесности к структуре текста. Антология / под общ. ред. В. П. Нерознака. М.: Academia, 1997. С. 267-269

According to some scientists, the concept is defined as an ideal abstract unit or a view of the object being studied by a person in its entirety.

In his research, Yu. S. Stepanov tries to reveal the essence of this term and first of all analyzes the etymology of the term "Concept". According to the research of Y. S. Stepanova, we can define the concept as "a collection of culture that is in the human mind, a part of the mental world of a person, when he enters the culture, in some cases it affects him."³⁷

According to J. Stepanov, "concept" is "like the main cultural cell in the human mental world, and also a mental structure that represents a person's knowledge about a certain segment of the world. To be a part of the image of the world, the concept reflects the values not only of a person, but also of the entire linguistic society. He said that while analyzing the concept from a cultural point of view, it should be remembered that its content remains in a certain period and culture.

The concept has been widely studied by many world linguists as a cognitive, psycholinguistic, linguistic and cultural phenomenon and it includes the subject areas of several scientific directions. In fact, language is not necessary for the formation of concepts, but for the exchange of concepts and discussion in the process of communication. Concepts exist in the real mentality of people, so they must be expressed orally, that is, using language tools, to communicate. In language, a concept can be expressed verbally by individual words, phrases, sentences or whole texts, depending on the concept itself. The choice of verbal form depends on the speaker's personal meaning, mental expression and internal lexicon, all of which are interrelated. The conditional component of the concept is stored in the mind in verbal form and can simply be described or interpreted.³⁸

At the current stage of linguistics, a number of approaches aimed at understanding and learning the concept can be distinguished. In different countries, researchers look at the concept as a linguistic, psycholinguistic, linguistic, cultural phenomenon, and each approach shows its own limits based on certain characteristics.

There are three different approaches to understanding the concept of language based on the function of forming the concept of language and showing the interrelationship of language with culture.

Proponents of the first approach (A.S. Askoldov-Alekseyev, D.S. Likhachev, V.N. Telia, etc.) study the concept as a linguistic phenomenon. In this regard,

³⁷ Степанов Ю.С. Концепты. Тонкая пленка цивилизации. – М.: Языки славянских культур, 2007. – 248 с.

³⁸ В.В. Завацкая. (n.d.). *ПОНЯТИЕ КОНЦЕПТА В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ КОГНИТИВНОЙ ЛИНГВИСТИКЕ*. <https://elib.bsu.by/bitstream/123456789/259018/1/40-42.pdf>

Askoldov lays the foundation stone for the study of the concept in Russian linguistics.

D.S. According to Likhachev, the concept does not only come from the meaning of the word, but it is the result of the collision of the personal experience of the person with the dictionary meaning of the word. "The wider and richer the potential of the concept, the richer the human experience."³⁹ Because, as the scientist described, the sum of concepts constitutes the concept sphere of a certain nation, and the richer the national conceptosphere is, the richer the culture of that nation is. The notion of the concept reflects the content of the results of human activity and the learning processes of the world, as well as the feelings of the participants in the thinking process, which affect the knowledge. As Likhachev noted, "concept" is an algebraic expression of the meaning that a person realizes in his written speech.⁴⁰

The representatives of the second approach (E.S. Kubryakova, Z.D. Popova, I.A. Sternin, V.Z. Demyankov) propose to study the synopsis as a linguistic-cognitive phenomenon. According to him, the concept is information about what a person knows, thinks, imagines and proposes about objects in our world. Proponents of this approach believe that any language is a system of concepts by which speakers of that language can interpret and classify the flow of information about the world around us.

Although the term concept is analyzed and studied differently in different fields of linguistics, E.S. Kubryakova defined it as a whole world view reflected in the human mind, a unit of operational memory and a unit of mental resources of our mind that serves for explanation, that is, a concept is created as a result of systematization of information about the properties of the imaginary world and objects.⁴¹ As described by E.S. Kubryakova, a person's system of ideas about the world includes verbal and non-verbal components as a conceptual image. "Concepts make it possible to store knowledge about the world and become structural elements of the conceptual system that processes objective experience by keeping the authorities on certain categories and classes created by society."⁴²

Well-known linguists such as Z.D. Popova and I.A. Sternin define the term "concept" as "a broad object or event that is the main unit of human mental

³⁹ Лихачев Д.С. Концептосфера русского языка // Русская словесность: От теории словесности к структуре текста: антол. / Под ред. В.П. Нерознака. М.: Academia, 1997.

⁴⁰ Лихачев Д.С. Концептосфера русского языка // Русская словесность. – М.: Academia, 1997. - С. 280-288

⁴¹ Кубрякова Е.С., Демьянков В.З., Панкрац Ю.Г., Лузина Л.Т. Краткий словарь когнитивных терминов. М.: Филол. ф-т, МГУ им. Ломоносова, 1997

⁴² Кубрякова и др. Краткий словарь когнитивных терминов / Под ред. Е.С. Кубряковой. М., 1996, С.12-90

potential, has a relatively orderly internal structure, is a product of the thoughts of a person and society, and reflects a special mental formation. "is a discrete unit of human thinking containing comprehensive, encyclopedic information" and interpreted this comment as social consciousness and the attitude of social consciousness to this event or topic. ⁴³According to them, while thinking, a person finds new concepts and thinks through them, and they give information that the result of applying the acquired knowledge can be a concept. They looked at concepts not as memories, but as units of thought. Z.D. According to the point of view of Popova and I. A. Sternin, ethnic-cultural identity and dignity are not mandatory for the concept, i.e. "The concept is the unity of the field of the concept is consciousness."⁴⁴

Supporters of the third approach (S.G. Vorkachev, G.G. Slishkin, V.I. Karasik) consider the concept as the main unit of culture. According to him, they consider the whole culture as a sum of concepts and relations between them. S.G. Vorkachev defines the concept as an operative unit of thought and defines it as a linguistic unit that reflects the spiritual essence and ethno-cultural identity that reflects the "people's spirit"⁴⁵. S. G. Vorkachev defines the concept as a separate object of collective consciousness, oriented to higher subjects, expressed in language and with ethno-cultural characteristics.

V.A. Maslova describes the concept as a semantic formation determined by linguistic and cultural identity and describing the owners of certain ethnic cultures in one way or another⁴⁶.

According to Lyapin, the self-organizing, integrated, functionally structured, multifaceted and idealized forms of the concept are based on the idea and depend on the content essence of the sign. For example, words or phrases in a diary, scientific terms, or complex lexical-grammatical, semantic structures, or subjective images and actions can be examples of this⁴⁷. A. Wierzbicka says that the concept is an object from the "ideal" world that reflects people's cultural understanding of the real world. The concept describes typical situations of culture and is the subject of cultural studies⁴⁸.

It is worth noting that Russian linguist R.M. Frumkin's concept is an object of conceptual analysis and that it is a way of "researching the way to understand the

⁴³ Popova Z. D., Sternin I. A. Semantiko-kognitivnyj analiz yazyka [Semantic-cognitive analysis of language].

⁴⁴ Попова З.Д., Стернин И.А. Когнитивная лингвистика. М.: АСТ: Восток-Запад, 2007.

⁴⁵ Воркачев С.Г. Счастье как лингвокультурный компонент. М.: ИТДГТ «Гнозис», 2004. –с.314

⁴⁶ Маслова В.А. Введение в когнитивную лингвистику / 5-е издание. М.: Флинта: Наука, 2011.

⁴⁷ Ляпин С.Х. Концептология: к становлению подхода // Концепты. Вып 1. – Архангельск, 1997. - С. 32-45.kr5n

⁴⁸ Wierzbicka A. 1980. The Case for Surface Case. Arbor 1980.

meaning of the concept and writing the result in a formalized semantic language". Conceptual analysis is a study in which the concept is the object of analysis. The meaning of conceptual analysis is, in its essence, the knowledge of the concept, that is, the concept is the knowledge of the object from the world of existence⁴⁹.

A. Vejbitskaya describes the concept as an object of the ideal world, which has its own name, is defined using a set of semantic data, and reflects cultural ideas about reality. Also, according to his opinion, the world of "truth" of a person reflects culturally defined concepts and is given for thinking through it, not only given by the truth⁵⁰.

It can be noted from the above definitions that different scientists put various features in the classification of the term concept in different periods. A.P. Babushkin defines the concept as lexical, phraseological, N.A. Krasavsky divides it into independent types from the structural-semantic point of view⁵¹.

⁴⁹ Фрумкина Р. М. Концептуальный анализ с точки зрения лингвиста и психолога // Научно-техническая информация. 1992. Сер. 2. № 3.

⁵⁰ Вежбицкая А. Семантические универсалии и описание языков. М.: Языки русской культуры, 1999. 780 с

⁵¹ Ангелова М.М. "Концепт" в современной лингвокультурологии / М.М. Ангелова // Актуальные проблемы английской лингвистики и лингводидактики. Сборник научных трудов. Выпуск 3. - М., 2004. - С. 3-10.